

Chemical speciation and computer modelling studies on interaction of an antioxidant 7,8-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin with bivalent metal ions

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Abstract : The stability constants of bivalent metal complexes with 7,8-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, an antioxidant are reported. The variation of stability constant with different ionic strengths, temperatures, percentage of solvents, dielectric constants have been studied by potentiometric estimation of H⁺ ions in the solution. The \bar{n} and pL values, thermodynamic parameters ΔG , ΔH and ΔS have been evaluated at 25 ± 0.5 °C. The values of δ_{\min} were also evaluated. Species distribution curves are plotted to visualize the nature of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexation equilibria at different H⁺ ions concentration.

Keywords : Antioxidants, bivalent metal ions, chemical speciation.

Coumarin derivatives are of biological interest because of their physiological, photodynamic, anticoagulant, spasmolytic, bacteriostatic, antitumor activity¹. Their complexing nature, widely used for elucidating the structure of natural flavonides, also contributes to the bioactivity of these compounds, by acting as carriers and regulators of metal concentration. Some coumarins possess a strong antioxidant effect due to their radical-scavenging activity and metal ion chelation²⁻⁴. 7,8-Dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (DHMC) inhibits lipid peroxidation by scavenging of free radicals or involving chelation of metal ions⁵.

In the present investigations complexation reactions of various bivalent metal ions at different H⁺ ions concentrations have been studied in solution. Energy minimized structure of complex has been established by computer modelling.

Results and discussion

Characterization of ligand :

UV spectra of ligand in methanol shows two absorption bands at 266 and 325 nm. IR spectra of ligand shows bands at 3350, 1670, 1590, 1450, 1360 and 1270 cm⁻¹. Proton NMR in DMSO-*d*₆ of ligands shows peaks at 2.20 (3H, s), 5.95 (1H, s), 6.65 (1H, d), 6.95 (1H, d), respectively. Mass spectra and elemental analysis also support the structure of ligand.

The stability constants for Cu^{II}, Pb^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Co^{II},

Cd^{II}, Fe^{II}, Mn^{II} and Mg^{II} are reported in Tables 1–3. The order of stability constants of the metal complexes with ligand DHMC is as follows : Cu^{II} > Pb^{II} > Ni^{II} > Zn^{II} > Co^{II} > Cd^{II} > Fe^{II} > Mn^{II} > Mg^{II} which is in good agreement with the order of Mellor and Maley⁶ and Irving and Williams^{7,8}.

In the present investigations it has been observed that the values of the dissociation constant of the ligand (pK_a) decreases with increase in ionic strength of the medium which is in agreement with the Debye-Hückel treatment as described in reference⁹.

A similar trend in variation was observed in the case of stability constants of the complexes (Table 1). This type of behaviour was also reported earlier¹⁰⁻¹². Thermodynamic stability constants ($\log K_1^0$), obtained by extrapolating the straight line plot of $\log K_1$ versus $\sqrt{\mu}$ to zero ionic strength are given in Table 1. The values of stability constants in Table 2 reveal that stability constants decreases with the increase in temperature along with the pK_a values. These results are in good agreement with those of Pitzer¹³. Thermodynamic parameters (ΔG , ΔH and ΔS) were calculated and are reported in Table 2. The negative values of ΔG and ΔH indicates that the complex formation reactions are favourable at ordinary temperatures, ΔS is positive for all the complexes showing that the entropy is favourable for the formation of all these complexes. The proton ligand constants and the formation constants of complexes of bivalent metal ions

with DHMC at temperature of 25 ± 0.5 °C and 0.1 M (NaClO₄) ionic strength have been evaluated in mixed aqua-DMF solvents and are given in Table 3. From Table 3 for a given mixed aqua-DMF solvent : 25% H₂O – 75% DMF, 35% H₂O – 65% DMF, 45% H₂O – 55% DMF, 55% H₂O – 45% DMF, it is clear that the pK_a of the ligand decreases with increase in water content of the aqua-DMF solvent. This may be due to increase in dielectric constant of

Table 1. Stability constants of bivalent metal complexes of DHMC in 25% H₂O – 75% DMF medium at different ionic strengths and at temperature 25 ± 0.5 °C

Metal ions	Stability constant	Ionic strength (M)				log K ₁
		0.02 M	0.05 M	0.1 M	0.2 M	
H ⁺		10.94	10.64	9.99	9.84	
Cu ^{II}	log K ₁	6.70	6.54	6.41	6.08	7.14
	log K ₂	6.28	6.03	6.00	5.21	
	δ _{min}	0.1809	0.0710	0.0479	0.0224	
Pb ^{II}	log K ₁	6.11	6.05	5.89	5.70	6.34
	log K ₂	5.57	5.60	5.59	4.71	
	δ _{min}	0.1146	0.2170	0.1960	0.0226	
Ni ^{II}	log K ₁	5.92	5.70	5.45	5.10	6.12
	log K ₂	5.15	5.09	4.85	4.40	
	δ _{min}	0.0370	0.0520	0.1397	0.0530	
Zn ^{II}	log K ₁	5.70	5.63	5.45	4.90	5.90
	log K ₂	4.92	4.80	5.00	4.40	
	δ _{min}	0.1594	0.0385	0.0667	0.0161	
Co ^{II}	log K ₁	5.00	4.91	4.98	4.12	5.80
	log K ₂	4.85	4.70	4.57	4.09	
	δ _{min}	0.1587	0.0460	0.0670	0.0794	
Cd ^{II}	log K ₁	5.10	5.07	4.56	4.10	5.18
	log K ₂	4.74	4.61	4.33	4.05	
	δ _{min}	0.1911	0.1783	0.0910	0.0829	
Fe ^{II}	log K ₁	4.72	4.76	4.45	3.50	4.94
	log K ₂	4.33	4.23	4.00	3.72	
	δ _{min}	0.0370	0.0360	0.0553	0.2340	
Mn ^{II}	log K ₁	3.93	4.10	3.88	3.50	4.60
	log K ₂	4.02	4.00	3.81	3.60	
	δ _{min}	0.2300	0.0910	0.0410	0.0713	
Mg ^{II}	log K ₁	4.31	3.70	3.69	3.00	4.38
	log K ₂	3.90	3.40	3.30	2.98	
	δ _{min}	0.0820	0.0692	0.0727	0.0129	

log K are the values of stability constants calculated by using weighted least squares method.

the medium, increase in hydrogen bonding ability and increase in proton solvation of the organic solvent. The data in Table 3 shows that the metal-ligand formation constant decreases with increase in the percentage of water in the medium :

The stability of the complexes containing either an O–H or O–M link decreases with increasing water^{14–16} which is due to increase in the dielectric constant of the bulk solvent. As the dielectric constant increases, the ion-ion interaction involving the proton (or metal ion) and the anionic

oxygen donor of the ligand decreases to a greater extent than the ion dipole interaction between the proton (or metal ion) and the solvent molecules.

Table 2. Stability constants of bivalent metal complexes of DHMC in 25% H₂O – 75% DMF medium at ionic strengths $\mu = 0.1$ M NaClO₄ and at different temperature

Metal ions	Stability constants	Temp. (°C)			–ΔG (kJ mol ^{–1})	–ΔH (kJ mol ^{–1})	ΔS (kJ mol ^{–1})
		30	40	50			
H ⁺		9.94	9.79	9.09			
Cu ^{II}	log K ₁	6.45	5.83	5.65	40.74	131.60	0.3048
	log K ₂	5.85	5.35	5.06			
	δ _{min}	0.0862	0.0792	0.0109			
Pb ^{II}	log K ₁	5.80	5.11	4.93	36.17	117.75	0.2736
	log K ₂	4.90	4.20	4.09			
	δ _{min}	0.0152	0.0293	0.0174			
Ni ^{II}	log K ₁	5.77	4.60	4.50	34.92	110.29	0.2529
	log K ₂	4.20	3.93	3.82			
	δ _{min}	0.0115	0.0272	0.1063			
Zn ^{II}	log K ₁	4.90	4.62	4.20	33.66	101.48	0.2276
	log K ₂	4.23	3.80	3.65			
	δ _{min}	0.0775	0.000597	0.0654			
Co ^{II}	log K ₁	4.82	4.52	3.36	33.09	100.33	0.2256
	log K ₂	3.89	3.48	2.99			
	δ _{min}	0.0065	0.0353	0.00019			
Cd ^{II}	log K ₁	4.35	4.20	3.80	29.55	88.08	0.1964
	log K ₂	3.77	3.20	3.50			
	δ _{min}	0.0266	0.0030	0.0405			
Fe ^{II}	log K ₁	4.05	3.90	3.23	28.19	86.16	0.1945
	log K ₂	3.43	3.17	2.72			
	δ _{min}	0.00079	0.00422	0.00631			
Mn ^{II}	log K ₁	3.96	3.61	3.30	26.25	86.54	0.2023
	log K ₂	3.64	3.03	2.20			
	δ _{min}	0.0644	0.00635	0.0005			
Mg ^{II}	log K ₁	4.00	2.72	2.55	24.99	74.67	0.1667
	log K ₂	3.44	1.93	1.64			
	δ _{min}	0.0161	0.000039	0.00003			

log K are the values of stability constants calculated by using weighted least squares method.

Species distribution study :

Species distribution curves of metal ions and DHMC system have been plotted as function of pH at a constant temperature of 25 ± 0.5 °C and 0.1 M (NaClO₄) ionic strength, using the program SPE. Species distribution curves are plotted to visualize the nature of the complexation equilibria and curves are given in Figs. 1–5. The percentage of various species which exist at different pH values are given in Table 4.

Fig. 1. Species distribution curves of Cu^{II}-DHMC complex.

Fig. 2. Species distribution curves of Pb^{II}-DHMC complex.

Fig. 3. Species distribution curves of Ni^{II}-DHMC complex.

Fig. 4. Species distribution curves of Zn^{II}-DHMC complex.

Fig. 5. Species distribution curves of Co^{II}-DHMC complex.

Molecular modelling studies :

The molecular modelling calculations on metal(II)-DHMC complexes were carried out using an interactive program¹⁷ that allows for rapid structure building, geometry optimization and molecular display. Energy minimization was repeated several times to find the global minimum. This supports octahedral geometry of the metal complexes. Fig. 6 (is a representative figure) shows the energy minimized structure of Fe^{II}-DHMC complex.

Table 3. Stability constants of bivalent metal complexes of DHMC in different % solvent at ionic strengths $\mu = 0.1 M NaClO_4$ and at temperature $25 \pm 0.5 ^\circ C$

Metal ions	Stability constants	Different % solvent			
		25% H ₂ O-75% DMF	35% H ₂ O-65% DMF	45% H ₂ O-55% DMF	55% H ₂ O-45% DMF
H ⁺		9.99	9.84	9.69	9.59
Cu ^{II}	log K ₁	6.41	6.40	6.30	6.15
	log K ₂	6.00	5.80	4.40	3.95
	δ_{min}	0.0479	0.2362	0.0138	0.0906
Pb ^{II}	log K ₁	5.89	5.79	5.37	5.15
	log K ₂	5.59	5.40	4.35	3.30
	δ_{min}	0.1960	0.1160	0.0176	0.0114
Ni ^{II}	log K ₁	5.45	5.35	5.09	4.90
	log K ₂	4.85	4.75	4.25	3.30
	δ_{min}	0.1397	0.0183	0.00921	0.0022
Zn ^{II}	log K ₁	5.45	5.00	4.90	4.60
	log K ₂	5.00	4.76	4.11	3.40
	δ_{min}	0.0667	0.0057	0.0638	0.0023
Co ^{II}	log K ₁	4.98	4.80	4.38	4.28
	log K ₂	4.57	4.50	3.64	2.80
	δ_{min}	0.0670	0.0653	0.0188	0.257
Cd ^{II}	log K ₁	4.56	4.30	3.95	3.75
	log K ₂	4.33	3.73	3.15	2.47
	δ_{min}	0.0910	0.0041	0.01427	0.00004
Fe ^{II}	log K ₁	4.45	4.00	3.43	3.50
	log K ₂	4.00	3.43	3.15	2.04
	δ_{min}	0.0553	0.0166	0.01497	0.00004
Mn ^{II}	log K ₁	3.88	3.68	3.62	3.40
	log K ₂	3.81	3.30	3.00	1.93
	δ_{min}	0.0410	0.0487	0.00163	0.000012
Mg ^{II}	log K ₁	3.69	3.60	3.35	3.23
	log K ₂	3.30	2.95	2.55	1.82
	δ_{min}	0.0727	0.00842	0.00053	0.00001

log K are the values of stability constants calculated by using weighted least squares method.

Fig. 6. Energy minimized structure of Fe^{II}-DHMC complex : (o) hydrogen, (●) carbon, (X) oxygen, (Y) ferrous ion.

Experimental

Preparation of DHMC :

To an ice-cold solution of pyrogallol in acetoacetic ester (1 : 1), concentrated sulphuric acid is added gradually over one hour with constant stirring, keeping the temperature at 273 K. The deep red viscous liquid so obtained is kept in a refrigerator (273–278 K) for about twenty-four hours and then poured into water with stirring. The precipitated solid

is filtered and washed with water, dried and then recrystallised from benzene where by a colourless crystalline solid is obtained.

Table 4. Species distribution as a function of pH

System	pH range, % ML complex	pH range for ML ₂ complex	Remarks
Cu ^{II} -DHMC	3.5–4.0, 45%	6.75–8.00, 100%	100% ML ₂ formed
Pb ^{II} -DHMC	3.75, 36%	7, 90%	Maximum complexation (ML ₂ formation) at neutral pH
Ni ^{II} -DHMC	4.0–5.0, 30%	8.5, 50%	No hydrolysis observed
Zn ^{II} -DHMC	4.0–5.0, 29%	8.0–9.0, 55%	At approximately neutral pH (pH 7.5) concentration of ML complex is zero
Co ^{II} -DHMC	3.5–4.0, 15%	7.0, 15%	At pH 9.5 concentration of ML ₂ complex is zero

The solution of DHMC was prepared first dissolving in DMF and then diluted with double distilled water. All the metal ion solutions were prepared in double distilled water. Sodium perchlorate was used to keep the ionic strength constant. A pre-standardised solution of tetramethylammonium hydroxide (TMAH) (E. Merck) in double distilled water was used as titrant. Other chemicals used were of reagent grade. The titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen which was presaturated with double distilled water. All measurements were made at a definite temperature (298 K) using a Julabo F20 (West Germany) thermostat.

The method of Bjerrum and Calvin as modified by Irving and Rossotti, has been used to determine \bar{n} and pL values. The experimental procedure involved potentiometric estimation of H⁺ ions of different solutions against standard 0.05 M TMAH solution at 25 ± 0.5 °C and at 0.1 M ionic strength as follows :

- (i) 2.5 mL HClO₄ (0.05 M) + 1.0 mL NaClO₄ (2.0 M) + 15 mL DMF + 1.5 mL H₂O.
- (ii) 2.5 mL HClO₄ (0.05 M) + 1.0 mL NaClO₄ (2.0 M) + 10 mL DHMC (0.01 M) in DMF + 5 mL DMF + 1.5 mL H₂O.
- (iii) 2.5 mL HClO₄ (0.05 M) + 1.0 mL NaClO₄ (2.0 M) + 0.5 mL metal ion (0.02 M) + 10 mL DHMC (0.01 M) in DMF + 5 mL DMF.

In other sets, a requisite amount of NaClO₄ was added to maintain the ionic strength at $\mu = 0.02, 0.05, 0.10$ and 0.20 M. The mixture at 0.1 M ionic strength was also individually titrated against TMAH at different temperatures viz. 25, 30, 40 and 50 ± 0.5 °C, at different % solvents : 25% H₂O – 75% DMF, 35% H₂O – 65% DMF, 45% H₂O – 55% DMF, 55% H₂O – 45% DMF.

From the above titration curves of solutions (i), (ii) and (iii) the values of \bar{n} and pL have been calculated using BEST program¹⁸. The corresponding values of stability constants have been calculated using the weighted least squares method of Sullivan *et al.*¹⁹. The weighted least squares treatment determines that the set of β_n values which makes the function

$$U \left[U = \sum_{n=0}^N (y - x - nz) \beta^n x^n \right]$$

nearest to zero by minimizing

$$S \left[S = \sum_{i=1}^I U^2 (x_i, y_i, z_i) \right]$$

with respect to the variation in β_n . In the above equations, y is the total ligand concentration, x is the total concentration of unbound ligand, z is the total metal ion concentration and β_n denotes stability constants.

We report the S_{\min} values for the different metal complexes. S_{\min} has the same statistical distribution as χ^2 with K degrees of freedom and with weights defined in accordance with Sullivan²⁰. S_{\min} can be equated to χ^2 . The stability constants calculated are given in Tables 1–3.

The minimization of energy of structure of the complex was obtained by force field calculation^{21,22}.

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